

D6.3 (M24) - Reports on the implementation of resources (an ELIXIR Norway ELIXIR₃ deliverable)

Project name: ELIXIR₃ - strengthening the Norwegian Node of ELIXIR

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Context

ELIXIR₃ - strengthening the Norwegian Node of ELIXIR, has engaged in the harmonisation of computational solutions for life science. This report, Deliverable 6.3, concerns the workflows, tools, and databases implemented for the processing of biodiversity data and datasets by Work Package 6 (WP6).

In biodiversity and life sciences research, the comparability of data across independent studies relies upon the harmonisation of processing and analysis. This necessitates the implementation of dedicated tools, workflows, storage and databases that align with the specific requirements of the scientific community. The integration of these components are to be facilitated through the Galaxy scientific workflow service and the Norwegian e-Infrastructure for Life Sciences (NeLS) platform. Alternatively, these elements may be deployed as stand-alone tools or encapsulated within containerized workflows published in ELIXIR supported repositories like bio.tools and WorkflowHub.eu.

One of the primary challenges addressed in this task is the need for standardised processing of sequence data by adhering to well documented and accepted systems. Achieving a high level of standardisation in biodiversity projects, such as the Earth BioGenome Project Norway (EBP-Nor), helps achieve FAIR, uniform, and comparative genomic data which can serve as models for other communities. This approach extends beyond EBP-Nor, as workflows will be made available to other projects with analogous requirements.

Delivery

- WP6 with BD has implemented Snakemake workflows for genome assembly and annotation in cooperation with the EBP-Nor project which can be operated under a Linux cluster environment.
 - The Snakemake workflows intended for haplotype-resolved genome assemblies (from PacBio HiFi and HiC reads) and annotations have been published on github and at WorkflowHub.eu:
 - <https://github.com/ebp-nor/GenomeAssembly>
 - <https://github.com/ebp-nor/GenomeAnnotation>
 - <https://workflowhub.eu/workflows/740>
- Workflows for the assembly and annotation of algae and diatom species is under development in WP6 by SP. Similar to the EBP-Nor workflow, these are planned to be published in ELIXIR channels upon completion and will be made available for application in external projects involving algae or diatom genomics.
- WP6 with T6.3 is in the planning stage of establishing and hosting a list of relevant biodiversity services for the biodiversity community. The services are targeted at molecular biodiversity datasets and will be presented through the ELIXIR Norway webpages (e.g., under elixir.no/rdm-lookup/biodiversity) and reviewed annually once operational.

Outcomes

- The implementation of assembly and annotation pipelines in collaboration with EBP-Nor is an important step towards ensuring uniformity of output data in the project. Even if the main purpose of the workflow is to serve EBP-Nor through the analysis of diploid eukaryotic species, the workflow is published and available to the wider community, benefitting from its design and functionality.
- WP6 with T6.3 aims to further implement and make available tools, workflows, or databases relevant for the biodiversity community. This includes niche specialised tools and workflows, like the algae/diatom workflow. These will further benefit the wider biodiversity community with tools or workflows built from special competence.
- Another aim for WP6 is to make tooling services findable and available to the wider community. As work package 6 is connected with stakeholders in Norwegian molecular biodiversity through T6.1, WP6 will analyse and respond to gaps in tooling needed by the community and list relevant and frequently used services under the ELIXIR Norway webpages.